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**INDIAN JOURNAL
OF
LANDSCAPE SYSTEMS AND
ECOLOGICAL STUDIES**

**Institute of
Landscape, Ecology & Ekistics**

Indian Journal of Landscape Systems and Ecological Studies

Volume : 41

No.2

December, 2018

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Dilip

Gender Disparity in Literacy: An Assessment of Kushinagar District, Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract : Literacy and education is considered as one of the important indicators of human development index and socio economic development of human. In Indian society, women have not been given equal opportunities when it comes to education as men has been given. The lagging behind of female literacy is one of the factors which kept the stagnation of technical, cultural, social and economic development of the society. There is a large gap in literacy between male and female found in most part of India. This paper has been prepared by using secondary data of two Census years 2001 and 2011 of Kushinagar district. The disparity has been calculated by using Sopher's disparity index. This paper shows an insight between male and female disparity in literacy in Kushinagar district. The findings suggest a significant spatio-temporal variation in male and female literacies among the blocks of the study area. In spite of several initiatives by the government, there are many illiterate people still existing in the society in which female numbers are more in comparison to males. The findings show a clear gap and disparity between male and female literacy in Kushinagar district of Uttar Pradesh.

Keywords : Gender disparity, Kushinagar, Literacy gap

Introduction

Education is the process to ease out learning, or acquiring knowledge and wisdom, ability, qualities, morality, beliefs and habits. Education is one of the most important factors of attaining the developmental goals. Education can bring the change in the success as well as growth of a nation. Education is not only important for a good social well-being but also a creative and productive well-being. Paternalistic culture, low level of economic opportunities and safety concern are the main barriers in female education (Roberts and Chittooran, 2016). Literacy is one of the most important indicators of socio-economic and political upliftment of a society. Patriarchy is one of the root causes for the bias in girls' education in comparison to boys' education, as parents prefer boys' education over the girls' education (Chaudhari and Roy, 2006).

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The upper caste fare better than backward and lower caste when education for both boys and girls is concerned, but caste doesn't appear to play a decisive role in the decision to make successive transition but classes do. Girls from lower caste and religious group do not encourage long term investment in education of girls than boys (Vaidya, 2004).

Through educational attainment women can achieve self-confidence, self-respect and can also discover their own capability of new ideas and innovations which will help in resisting to their gender discrimination. Women's education and employment are determining factors in fertility behaviour and help in job creation which will lead to family welfare (Heptulla, 2000). Education makes women independent and they can take their own decision. When we look at the entire human population, the share of educated women is much lower than men. Education could boost the women to come forward and contribute to the development of the country. If the women remain educationally lagging behind and economically dependent on men, their condition will not change much. So to become self-esteemed and self-reliant, they have to be educated so that they can take their own decision independently.

Education makes women aware about their rights for justice. And this would lead in declining of violence and injustice against the women as dowry, forced prostitution, child marriage, female feticide, etc. every girl must be given equal opportunity to become a successful doctor, engineer, nurse, air hostess, administrative officer, cook, or whatever her choices would she choose to become. Among the social groups the *dalits* have lower literacy rate apart from the Muslim women but they will serve as a catalyst in development if they will be given equal opportunities in education (Benzamin, 2008). Literate women in Kushinagar are lagging far behind the men and they also lag behind in national average. There are several reasons for the low literacy of women in the Kushinagar district such as poverty, gender, unemployment, illiteracy, child marriage, and distance of school/college from home, security of female child, patriarchal society (Limaye 2016). Literacy rate of schedule caste women and Muslim women are less in comparison to other category of women, social factors are more responsible for such disparity.

Study Area

Kushinagar district is a part of Gorakhpur division in eastern Uttar Pradesh, its district headquarter is located at Padrauna town. The district is famous for the Mahaparinirvana of Mahatma Buddha. Since 13th May, 1994, the district came into existence, earlier it was a part of Deoria district. The district has an area of 2905 sq km, and it is bounded by Bihar State in the East, Deoria in the South, Gorakhpur district on the West and Maharjganj district in the North-West. The climate in the district remains extremely hot in summer and moderately cold during the winter season.

At present, the district has been divided into 6 sub-divisions including Padrauna, Kasia, Hata, Tamkuhi Raj, Khadda and Kaptanganj. The district has been also divided into fourteen Community Development Blocks namely Kaptanganj, Ramkola, Motichak, Hata, Sukrauli, Khadda, Nebuwa Naurangiya, Vishunpura, Padrauna, Kasia, Dudhai, Fazil nagar, Tamkuhi and Sevarahi.

Limaye

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LOCATION MAP OF KUSHINAGAR DISTRICT, U.P.

Fig.1: Location map of Kushinagar district, UP

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According to the 2011 census Kushinagar district has a population of 35, 64,544 persons in which 18, 18,055 are males and 17, 46,489 are females. The district has a sex ratio of 961 females per 1000 males. The district has a population density of 1226 inhabitants per square kilometre. Its population growth rate over the decade 2001-2011 was 23.08 per cent in which 23.37 per cent are male growth rate whereas female has a growth rate of 23.03 per cent. The district has made a slight progress in the field of education through various progressive steps. The district has a total literacy rate as 67.25 per cent in which female literacy rate is 52.36 per cent whereas male literacy rate is 77.71 per cent. The district has population majorly belonging to Hindu and Muslim religion consisting of 82.16 per cent and 17.40 per cent of population respectively. Agriculture is the backbone as far as economy is concern. People are engaged in agriculture because the industrialization is negligible in the district.

Objectives

The objectives of this study are:

- To assess the disparity in literacy between male and female population in Kushinagar district
- To find out the factors determining the disparity in literacy in the district

Data Sources and Methodology

This study is primarily based on secondary data sources mainly obtained from the publications of Census of India and other publications. The data of the decadal change from 2001 to 2011 has been collected from the District Census Handbook of Kushinagar District of 2001 and 2011, Primary Census Abstract, General Population Tables, several literature and books, articles, published as well as non-published materials has been dealt for the study. The blocks are considered as the basic unit of this study because it will give the best glimpse of thorough study for which data of block level is available. The data has been analysed in Microsoft Excel. The analysis and interpretation has been done through textual and tabular formats followed by the result and discussions. The block wise variation has been shown on the maps through Arc GIS 10.1. The maps have been collected from District Census Handbook of Kushinagar District 2011. To achieve the objectives of the study Sopher's disparity index has been used to find out the block wise disparity of male female literacy of Kushinagar district from 2001 to 2011 Census. Sopher's Disparity Index is well accepted measurement to identify the disparity in male female literacy. So according to Sopher's Disparity Index technique, if X_1 and X_2 represent the respective percentage value of the variables of group A and group B then the Disparity Index can be calculated as,

$$DI = \log (X_2/X_1) + \log \{(100-X_1)/(100-X_2)\}$$

Where, DI= Disparity Index

X_1 = percentage of female literates

X_2 = percentage of male literates

i.e., $X_2 \geq X_1$

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Higher the value of Disparity Index will show the higher inequality in genders and lower the Disparity will show the lesser inequality between the genders. The perfect equality between the genders will be at zero Disparity Index. Hence, Sopher's Disparity Index is very useful in measuring the relative disparity. This study mainly focuses on the rural population of the Kushinagar district because 95.7 per cent of the population reside in the rural area whereas only 4.3 per cent are the urban population. The factors affecting disparity in education has been fulfilled through observation method, interaction with people and through several literatures. Poverty, gender, unemployment, illiteracy, child marriage, and distance of school/college from home, security of female child, patriarchal society are the factors affecting educational disparity between the genders (Limaye, 2016).

Results and Discussion

Spatio -Temporal Change in Literacy Rate of 2001 and 2011 in Kushinagar District

India is a diverse country and diversity can be seen in every field. In literacy rate, variation can be easily observed in state to state and region to region. If we look at the literacy rate of Uttar Pradesh it has never been above the nation average till the last Census 2011. In Uttar Pradesh itself, a large variation can be seen in literacy rate among the districts. So as in the cause of Kushinagar

Table 1: C D Block Wise Change in Literacy Rate in Kushinagar District, 2001-2011

Blocks	Literacy rate (2001)	Literacy rate (2011)	Change
Khadda	34.1	58.0	23.9
Nebua Naurangiya	42.5	63.98	21.48
Vishunpura	41.5	61.71	20.21
Padrauna	49.1	66.07	16.97
Kaptanganj	50.0	68.5	18.5
Ramkola	45.3	64.79	19.49
Motichak	47.3	67.5	20.2
Sukrauli	50.8	68.56	17.76
Hata	54.0	69.88	15.88
Kasiya	52.6	68.9	16.3
Fazilnagar	52.6	69.88	17.28
Tamkuhi Raj	50.9	67.85	16.95
Dudhahi	35.1	57.28	22.18
Sevrahi	38.6	58.98	20.38
Total	45.8	64.75	18.95

Source- District Census handbook of Kushinagar, 2001-11

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Fig. 2: Spatio-Temporal Change in Literacy Rate in Kushinagar, UP, 2001-2011

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district it has never been above the national or state average literacy rate. The total literacy rate of the study area in 2001 was only 45.8 per cent which has increased to 64.75 per cent in the year 2011 (Table 1). So, a significant change of 18.95 per cent has been registered over a decade.

Among the blocks, Hata (54 per cent), Kasiya (52.6 per cent), Fazilnagar (52.6 per cent), Tamkuhi Raj (50.9 per cent), Sukrauli (50.8 per cent), Kaptanganj (50 per cent), Padrauna, Motichak have high literacy rate 2001 whereas Ramkola, Nebua Naurangiya and Vishunpura has the moderate literacy rate while Khadda (34.1 per cent), Dudhahi (35.1 per cent) and Sevrahi (38.6 per cent) have the lowest literacy rate in the 2001 Census. The main reason behind the lowest literacy rate among these blocks was the unavailability of basic infrastructure and also these blocks also border with Bihar which has lowest literacy in the country that might be the reason also. But if we look at the 2011 Census Fazilnagar (69.88 per cent), Hata (68.9 per cent), Sukrauli (68.56 per cent), Kaptanganj and Motichak have the highest literacy rate The reason behind the improvement in literacy is establishment in of school/colleges and midday meal program in the primary schools. The other blocks also have improved significantly during these 10 years. The highest change can be observed in Khadda (23.9 per cent) and lowest (15.88 per cent) whereas the average change in the district was 18.95 per cent.

Literacy Rate and Gap between Male and Female, 2001-2011

There is variation in literacy rate and gap in male female can be observed in all the blocks. In 2001, the highest male and female literacy rate can be observed as 72.7 per cent (Hata) and 36.5 per cent (Hata) respectively and the lowest male and female literacy rate found as 48.6 per cent (Khadda) and 18.2 per cent (Khadda) respectively whereas the average male female literacy rate was 62.8 and 28.33 respectively. The standard deviation can be observed as 7.61 and 6.42 in male female respectively (Table 2&3). So, a significant gap can be found in all the blocks. But if we look at the Census year 2011, there is significant improvement in all the blocks can be observed. The highest male and female literacy rate can be observed as 83.15 per cent (Hata) and 57.28 per cent (Fazilnagar) respectively. Whereas the lowest male and female literacy rate found as 70.07 per cent (Dudhahi) and 43.81 per cent (Dudhahi) respectively and the average male female literacy rate are found as 77.51 per cent and 51.595 respectively. When we look at the standard deviation of male and female

Table 2: Male-Female Statistics of Literacy Rate, 2001-2011

Literacy Rate		Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Male } Female }	2001	62.8	7.61	48.6	72.7
		28.3	6.42	18.2	36.5
Male } Female }	2011	77.51	6.81	70.07	83.15
		51.59	4.72	43.81	57.28

Source: Computed by the researchers

literacy rate, it is found as 6.81 and 4.72 respectively. So, we can find that there is improvement in all the blocks but difference in male to male, female to female and region to region is observed in all the blocks.

Table 3: Literacy Rates and Gender Gap in Kushinagar District, 2001-11

Serial no.	CD Blocks	Literacy Total	Literacy Male	Literacy Female	Gap	Literacy Total	Literacy Male	Literacy Female	Gap
2001					2011				
1	Khadda	34.1	48.6	18.2	30.4	58	70.63	44.39	26.24
2	Nebua Naurangiya	42.5	61.3	22.5	38.8	63.98	77.63	49.63	28
3	Vishunpura	41.5	58.1	23.3	34.8	61.71	74.52	48.32	26.2
4	Padrauna	49.1	65.1	32.4	32.7	66.07	77.85	53.75	24.1
5	Kaptanganj	50	67.6	31.4	36.2	68.5	81.04	55.57	25.47
6	Ramkola	45.3	63.1	26.5	36.6	64.79	78.08	50.8	27.28
7	Motichak	47.3	65.8	29	36.8	67.5	80.74	53.38	27.36
8	Sukrauli	50.8	69.7	31.9	37.8	68.56	82.25	54.96	27.29
9	Hata	54	72.7	36.5	36.2	69.88	83.15	56.75	26.4
10	Kasiya	52.6	69.5	35.1	34.4	68.9	80.98	56.38	24.6
11	Fazil Nagar	52.6	70.2	35.8	34.4	69.88	82.54	57.28	25.26
12	Tamkuhi Raj	50.9	68.8	33.4	35.4	67.85	80.86	54.93	25.93
13	Dudhahi	35.1	50.9	18.3	32.6	57.28	70.07	43.81	26.26
14	Sevrahi	38.6	54.4	22.3	32.1	58.98	71.67	45.63	26.04
	Total	45.8	62.8	28.3	34.5	64.75	77.51	51.59	25.92

Source: District Census handbook Kushinagar, 2001 and 2011

Male-Female Disparity in Literacy, 2001-2011

The disparity between male and female is always been a case of concern and it has a past history of having a disparity gap between the two genders. According to Sopher's disparity index there is no disparity when the value of disparity index will be zero and it will be high when the value will be one. Here, male-female disparity has been divided into three categories in the study area high, medium and low i.e. (0.691-0.750), (0.641-0.690) and (0.590-0.640) respectively in the year 2001. In the year 2011, the disparity has been decreased in all the blocks in which high ranges between (0.546-0.576), medium (0.495-0.545) and low (0.476-0.494). Higher disparity index in 2001 was 0.741 in Nebua Naurangiya block whereas lowest disparity index was in padrauna (0.590) (Figure 4). But in

2011; highest disparity index was in Sukrauli (0.576) and lowest was in Dudhahi (0.476). The reason behind decrease in disparity might be increasing number of schools/colleges, awareness among the people towards female education, government programmes like 'Sarva Siksha Abhiyan', 'Sab Padhe Sab Badhe', midday meal programme, etc.

Table 4: Block wise Disparity index in Kushinagar District, 2001-11

Serial no.	Blocks	Literacy Male	Literacy Female	Disparity Index (2001)	Literacy Male	Literacy Female	Disparity Index (2011)
1	Khadda	48.6	18.2	0.627	70.63	44.39	0.477
2	Nebua Naurangiya	61.3	22.5	0.741	77.63	49.63	0.545
3	Vishunpura	58.1	23.3	0.658	74.52	48.32	0.494
4	Padrauna	65.1	32.4	0.59	77.85	53.75	0.481
5	Kaptanganj	67.6	31.4	0.658	81.04	55.57	0.53
6	Ramkola	63.1	26.5	0.674	78.08	50.8	0.537
7	Motichak	65.8	29	0.66	80.74	53.38	0.534
8	Sukrauli	69.7	31.9	0.69	82.25	54.96	0.576
9	Hata	72.7	36.5	0.665	83.15	56.75	0.573
10	Kasiya	69.5	35.1	0.624	80.98	56.38	0.517
11	Fazil Nagar	70.2	35.8	0.624	82.54	57.28	0.51
12	Tamkuhi Raj	68.8	33.4	0.641	80.86	54.93	0.534
13	Dudhahi	50.9	18.3	0.664	70.07	43.81	0.476
14	Sevrahi	54.4	22.3	0.617	71.67	45.63	0.478
	Total	62.8	28.3	0.631	77.51	51.59	0.5

Source: District Census handbook Kushinagar 2001 and 2011

In 2001, Nebua Naurangiya has the high disparity index (0.691- 0.750) whereas Vishunpura, Dudhahi, Ramkola, Kaptanganj, Motichak, Hata and Sukrauli have medium disparity index (0.641-0.690) and low disparity index (0.590-0.640) has been found in Padrauna, Kasiya, Khadda, Fazilnagar, Tamkuhi raj and Sevrahi. In 2011, high disparity index (0.546-0.576) was found in Sukrauli and Hata, whereas medium disparity index (0.495-0.545) was found in the blocks of Nebua Naurangiya, Ramkola, Kasiya, Fazil nagar and Tamkuhi raj and low disparity index (0.476-0.494) was found in Khadda, Vishunpura, Padrauna, Dudhahi and Sevrahi blocks (Figure 4). Some blocks have improved in terms

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Fig. 3: Comparison of Disparity Index in Kushinagar, 2001-2011

Source: Calculated by the researchers based on data from District Statistical Handbook, Kushinagar District, 2001-2011

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disparity from high to low and these blocks are Nebua Naurangiya, Vishunpura and Dudhahi while some has move low to medium and high, these blocks are Sukrauli and Hata (medium to high) and Kasiya, Fazilnagar and Tamkuhi Raj (low to medium). But if we look at the overall blocks all the blocks has done better improvement in eliminating the disparity in literacy.

Fig. 4: Disparity index of Male-Female literacy Rate, 2001-2011

Source: Calculated by the researchers based on data from District Statistical Handbook, Kushinagar District, 2001-2011

Factors Affecting the Disparity in Literacy between Male and Female

There are several reasons for the low literacy of women in the Kushinagar district such as poverty, gender, unemployment, illiteracy, child marriage, and distance of school/college from home, security of female child, patriarchal society, etc. some factors are as follow:

Poverty

India is overpopulated country, so despite of several efforts of government, the literacy in rural areas have not improved much. Girls from poor family suffer the most when it comes to education as poor families do not focus on their education because they found it hard to provide facilities for which is costly now a days. Because of poverty parents could not provide the education for both male and female so they prefer boys' education than girls' education. Thus, poverty leads to disparity in male and female literacy.

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Gender

When the parents cannot afford the education of children then they prefer son's education at first over the daughter. It has been long lasting disparity prevailing in India. Girls always suffer the dropouts when parents do not provide education for both boys and girls. If we look at the national level there is 63.5 per cent drop out in adolescent girls. Indian families spend more on daughters' marriage than spending on their education. In a poverty laden family, every penny is spent on basic needs and education of boys without any question, although the daughter perform better than son it will not matter they will prefer boys' education first, so it is unfortunate that education is decided based on sex in place of ability. There is an African proverb "if you educate a man you educate an individual but if you educate woman educate a generation." So, education of women is the need of the hour.

Education of Parents

Education of parents play important role in literacy rate of female. Educated parents can take better decision to educate their children and they know the importance of education for better future. The education of mother and father also influences the schooling and post schooling of girls as mother's education affect schooling and father's education affect girl's education (Vaidya, 2004). The literacy rate in the study area in the past was not good and that is one of the reason for the low literacy and disparity between the genders.

Accessibility

Accessibility is also very important factor affecting the literacy of not only females but also males though it affects the female literacy particularly. The distance of school/colleges from home determines the educational enrolment of female child more in comparison to male child. With increasing the distance of school/college from home there is decreasing rate of enrolment found in the study area. Road transport plays important role in travelling as good road provide better accessibility but poor quality of roads in the district reduces the enrolment of female child in schools and colleges as most of the good schools are in towns. School premise also important as many schools doesn't have the facilities of washroom for female, libraries, sitting facilities, playgrounds, water facilities, security, etc. Though these facilities have been improved at some extent but it still needs to be improved. There is difference in public and private schools as private schools provide good quality of education but it cost more for the parents to afford the education of female child. Also most of the good schools are in the towns so travelling is also determining the literacy of female and male child.

Child Marriage

Child marriage is one the major reason that affects the literacy of the females. When a child girl is forced to marry she faces problem with immediate as well as consequences, there is hindrance not only in her education but also the chances of abuse and exploitation by her husband could be happen. According to National Family Health Survey-4 statistics, 31.6 per cent female of 20-24years

age group married before attaining the age of 18 years in the study area. 3.9 per cent female of age group 15-19 years who are already mothers or pregnant at the time of survey in 2015-16 in the study area. So it is clear that child marriage has been quite prevailing. Apart from the reported data there are several cases are there in which child marriage are prevalent but the parents kept the age as secret because of the law. Parents presume daughters as burden and they want to marry them as soon as possible.

Society

Patriarchy is the root cause of male-female disparity in literacy. The main perception of the society is that girls have to marry one day and they will leave for their in-laws home so they will not add any economic benefits so they do not think about the girls' education much. In future, these girls will be known as illiterate mothers which might work as chain reaction for the future generation of daughters and they would be treated as same, which could again leads to female illiteracy.

Government Policy

Though there are several government programs for improvement of female education like Sakshar bharat mission for female literacy (2008), Right to Education, Kasturba Balika Vidyalaya, National Programme for Education of Girls at Elementary level, Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan, Dhanlakshmi scheme, etc. through these programs there is improvement in the female literacy rate but there is a huge disparity is there in male and female literacy is still there. There is need of improvement in female literacy from every home and it can be improved as:

- When each and every one do not consider female as burden and provide them equal opportunities to them.
- We should stop thinking that they should stick only to cooking, washing clothes and other household activities.
- They should be given equal opportunities and respect
- They should be set free to choose about their own career.
- We should encourage everyone to educate female child without any discrimination

There should be holistic education where women should not only think of degree oriented study but they should attain career defining opportunities and start earning money through education.

Conclusion

The study reveals that there is significant increase in literacy rate in the study area during the 10 years (2001 to 2011) from 45.8 per cent to 64.75 per cent so an increase of 18.95 per cent can be observed which is very good. But there can be variation in male and female literacy rate can be observed in all the blocks. The study also reveals that disparity between male and female has been decreased but it is still high in all the blocks of the Kushinagar district. There are several factors

which determine the literacy has to be looked to reduce the gap between male and female literacy. Government has implemented several plans and policies for the improvement and development of female education but we should also contribute in better way for the uplift of female literacy. The disparity has been reduced when each and every one do not consider female as burden and provide them equal opportunities to them. We should stop thinking that they should stick only to cooking, washing of clothes and other household activities. They should be given equal opportunities and respect. They should be set free to choose about their own career. We should encourage everyone to educate female child without any discrimination. There should be holistic education where women should not only think of degree oriented study but they should attain career defining opportunities and start earning money through education.

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Received : 2nd September, 2018

Revised : 14th October, 2018